

Coding guide

Deductive coding guide

Coding guide based on the dimensions derived from literature prior to revision

Category	Definition	Anchor examples
Adaptability to user requirements	The device should be easily adjustable to users' individual needs. Users should be able to adjust themselves.	"I don't like always pricking the same finger with the needle. Therefore, I like the ability to choose any finger by myself"
Adequate functionality	The functionality of the device should be appropriate. This means that the device has a reasonable/target number and type of functions or possibilities dependent on the area of application. The device should have all necessary functions but not more than required.	"I like the number of functions. The device has all the features I need for successful application but no unnecessary bells and whistles"
Aesthetics (haptic, visual, acoustic)	The device should have an appealing design. This can refer to its appearance, the sounds produced, and the haptics, e.g., the impression when touching it.	"I think the device looks good and feels great"
Clarity of use	The relevant functions of the device should be displayed explicitly or easy to understand.	"I really like the fact that I can directly identify which button I have to press for my intended function"
Comfort of use for the user	The device should be pleasant in design and application.	"It is comfortable to hold the device during use"
Conformity with user expectations	The reactions of the device during use are as expected. There is internal and external consistency in the responses of the device. Changes of the use context are detected, e.g., a clinical thermometer registers a change in temperature.	"When I press the volume button on my hearing device, the volume increases at the same rate each time"
Controllability	Users should be able to control the device easily and reliably. It should be possible to interrupt the application, the device should be flexible in use, and it should be customizable to a reasonable extent.	"I have good control over the device. The stop button gives me the possibility to interrupt the application every time"
Effectiveness	The device should have high effectiveness. This means, the application leads to the intended goal, respectively the device should be suitable for achieving this goal.	"By using the blood glucose meter, I can identify my current blood glucose level"
Efficiency	The device should be efficient in use so that high productivity is possible for a skilled user. This means, the required effort for successful use should be reasonable.	"The application is very fast, so I can treat many patients successfully in a short time"
Error rate	The error rate should be low so that few errors or problems occur during the application and arising ones can be easily corrected.	"If an error occurs, I can easily correct it"
Fun of use	Handling the device should be fun or enjoyable for the person using it.	"Using the device is a pleasure"
Influence on emotions	The device should not cause negative emotions, such as stress and similar states, during application.	"I like the fact that despite the difficult context, my emotions remain unchanged. The application of the device does not stress me psychologically"
Intuitive design	The design of the device should be self-evident and intuitive.	"It is obvious how the device should be used and why it was designed that way"
Intuitive use	The operation of the various device functions should be self-evident and intuitive. Thus, it does not take much time to figure out which operation is needed for achieving the intended goal.	"Whenever I use the device, it is self-evident to me how to operate the product for achieving my intended goal"
Learnability	The use of the device should be easy to learn so that users are quickly able to use it. The device should support the user in discovering, trying out, remembering, and recognizing operating functions.	"I was quickly able to use the device independently because the learning process was easy"
Memorability	Remembering the decisive aspects for using the device should be easy so that after a long period without use, it is not necessary to relearn everything.	"I use the medical device rarely but I still remember how to use it very well"

Category	Definition	Anchor examples
Originality	The device should be novel, innovative, and special in nature compared to other devices.	"I have never seen such a great and special device. It was really something new"
Reliability	The device should be dependable in use and reliably fulfill its functions. In other words, the application should have consistency and the device always react in the same way.	"When I press the green button, I can be sure that I will get the result I need in the same way every time"
Safety	The device should be safe to use. Consequently, there should be no hazards associated with device use. There should be no risks associated with it or they should be proportionate to the benefits of the device.	"In my experience, using the device is very safe as accidents have never occurred during its use"
Self-descriptiveness	When using the device, information that explains and facilitates its use should be present and obvious. The system status of the device should be clearly displayed, e.g., in the case of an electronic clinical thermometer.	"It is easy to understand how the device should be used because all the necessary information is displayed"
Suitability for the user's tasks	It should be clear what task the device is intended to assist with. It should be possible to optimize the effort required when completing the task. If it makes sense, the device offers standard selection options (defaults) for use, e.g., different programs that can be selected depending on the specific nature of the task.	"I quickly understand what I should use the device for"
User engagement	Users should feel an attachment to the device. This can be generated by, e.g., the application evoking user motivation, generating a sense of trustworthiness, and/or causing integration/involvement of the user.	"When I use the clinical thermometer, I am motivated to use it again in a timely manner"
Use error robustness	Use errors occurring during application should be avoided, tolerated, or resolved by the device.	"If errors occur during use, they are corrected by the device or do not pose a problem for use"
User satisfaction	The application of the device should be fitting so that users are subjectively satisfied during use and/or with the result of the application.	"The application of the device leaves no further wishes and I am satisfied with the result"
User trust	Users should have confidence in the device when using it and be able to rely on it. Trust in this case means subjectively perceived trust.	"I am not afraid to use the product because I trust it completely"

Inductive coding guide

Inductively formed categories of usability and UX of medical devices

Category	Definition	Anchor examples
Accuracy	The result of the device should be exact enough for the person using it to obtain the information they need as accurately as needed.	<p>“The use of the insulin pen is very, very accurate”</p> <p>“It does not always reflect the child’s doing to a hundred percent”</p>
Adequate sensitivity	The device should react appropriately to relevant stimuli during use and identify relevant aspects, meaning that it should not react too strongly to stimuli or be too insensitive for decisive stimuli which should be identified or reacted to.	<p>“The test strips are relatively sensitive if you do not put enough blood on them”</p> <p>“I wish that the systems or that the devices would not react so sensitively“</p>
Alternative option	The possibility of achieving a certain goal should not be limited to one device. Instead, there should be at least one other device able to fulfill the same purpose. Accordingly, the device may serve to control or replace another one or may itself be replaced by another device if the user has doubts regarding its accuracy or efficiency.	<p>“Then I’d rather measure again with the blood glucose meter”</p>
Automatisation of use	The medical device or the system of medical devices automates process steps that would normally be carried out by the user. This is done, e.g., by digitally transmitting values from one device to another, the latter of which in turn automatically adjusting its response based on the transmitted values.	<p>“I wish that the device would work in an automated way in the long run and inject insulin on an automatic basis.”</p>
Comfort of use for the patient	The product should not be unpleasant in design and use for the patient on whom another person is using the product.	<p>“It is also unpleasant for the patient“</p>
Consistency between manufacturers	The application of the product should be comparable between the same devices from different manufacturers. That implies that the application should always work the same way in essence.	<p>“It would be great if you at least always knew how to use the product as a consequence of products working the same way independently of the manufacturer“</p>
Durability / operating time	The device should have acceptable durability. This means that it should not break or be damaged on a regular basis making extensive repairs or complete replacement necessary. The regular runtime determined by the battery life, e.g., should also be of a reasonable length.	<p>“It does not stick long enough”</p> <p>“This device just runs for a very long time”</p> <p>“The battery life of some head-lamps is quite disappointing“</p>
Easy use	The device should be easy to use. Thus, it should not be complicated in use. Complex individual steps, e.g., should not result in unnecessarily complicated processes.	<p>“It was so uncomplicated”</p> <p>“It is easy to handle”</p>
Error handling	The device should provide information on error messages so that the user can easily correct them. This refers to error representation as well as to the subsequent solution finding process.	<p>“Error messages did not give much information about opportunities to solve them”</p> <p>“It would make a difference if a concrete error message appeared with helpful information to fix the error“</p>
Facilitation of everyday life	The device makes daily life easier for the user, e.g., when compared to no product or the use of other products (e.g., fewer operating steps and thus perceived ease of use).	<p>“It also made life a little easier”</p>
Facilitation of work	The use of the device should make the task easier for the person using it compared to the work without it. That means, work should be eliminated for the person in some way.	<p>“It made the actual work a lot easier“</p>
Feedback of the device	The medical device provides information/feedback on specific user actions during device use. E.g., an insulin pump may beep or vibrate when the programmed insulin dose has been injected.	<p>“It beeps to show that it worked. That way, you also have an acoustic signal and you always know: Okay, it worked”</p>
Flexibility of use environment	The device should be flexible regarding the environment or rather the place or the facilities in which it can be used. That means, it should not be tied to specific surroundings. Likewise, it should be possible to use it flexibly within a room.	<p>“If you have a relatively quiet room, you can perform this hearing test almost anywhere because the headphones cancel the noise much better“</p>
Handiness in everyday situations	The device should be manageable and be able to be carried around in daily situations without any major inconvenience (e.g., due to weight, size, bulkiness).	<p>“I don’t like to take the heavy device with me in situations like that”</p>
Inconspicuousness	The device is unobtrusive in everyday life, either for the person using it or for the environment. The device can be applied easily and “in private”, even in social situations.	<p>“I had the insulin pump on my back and it was more or less hidden”</p>

Category	Definition	Anchor examples
Increase of autonomy	The device gives the user a certain degree of independence in dealing with their medical condition, resulting in greater independence from (more) regular visits to the doctor and inpatient examinations. The user can, e.g., determine relevant values on their own and make appropriate medication adjustments.	“And this gives me a lot of freedom, I don't have to go to the doctor, I can measure everything on my own”
Integration into everyday life	The use of the device can be well included into daily life without the user having to accept major inconveniences, being restricted, or having to interrupt activities for a longer period. This includes that the application can take place “in passing” and that the product does not require excessive attention.	“In that situation, I didn't have to get up, I didn't have to leave the room. Instead, I said, “Okay, I will eat this and then I will inject a certain amount of insulin””
Patient health	The device should not cause harm to the patient's health as a result of its use. For example, exposure to radiation would negatively affect health.	“It works without damaging any surrounding tissues“
Physical integrity	The device can be used without causing discomfort to the user due to somatic impairment. For example, the product does not have to be permanently worn or attached to the body, which eliminates resulting potential inconvenience factors. Another example would be that users do not have to take a drop of blood using a lancing device each time a blood glucose test is performed.	“That way, you don't have to prick your finger anymore” “You had scarred fingertips when using the regular lancing device at that time”
Product tolerance	The device should be compatible for the user which means that no allergies etc. should occur.	“I was allergic to the patch”
Purpose-related applicability	The device should include all necessary elements for its adequate use and they should be usable to the intended extent.	“This tube is also properly inserted into the device so that it can measure correctly”
Self-efficacy	The user experiences self-efficacy when using the device. Self-efficacy refers to a person's confidence that he or she can successfully carry out desired actions based on his or her own competencies, even in extreme situations.	“Then, I had a good feeling and I thought, “Ah, you can still do it””
Supervision of status	The device state can be monitored by the user. The current status can be tracked. In addition, value trends over a certain time period, e.g., can be mapped and consequently analysed, making it easier to classify the significance of the current value.	“It is depicted very well on the trajectory “ “Every time I look at the insulin pump, I see the current blood glucose value”
Technical tying	Various medical devices are connected to each other as part of an interconnected system. They can communicate or individual medical devices can be (remotely) controlled by other, technically connected devices.	“The sensor communicates with the pump”
Time-efficient maintenance	The device does not require much additional care so that the time required for maintenance, e.g., for cleaning and care, is in reasonable proportion to the benefits of the product.	“It would be more comfortable if the cleaning process was easier. You have to disinfect it very often” “It is easy to clean“
Visual representation	The visual representation of the device should be of high quality, meaning that the presentation of content is chosen in a way that is adequate and user-friendly. Visual presentation means the visual illustration of relevant information, e.g., on a display. This includes ensuring that display surfaces are easy to read and users can easily identify information, e.g., through contrast, resolution, or the size of the relevant elements.	“The display is large and easy to read.” “It must have a very good resolution” “It has a very good image quality”
Warning function	The device should have a warning function. This means, if dangerous situations occur during use, the product should alert the person using it to increase the safety of use.	“It also has such a warning function and indicates when something is wrong“